

Report on **Milestone 43**

Marketplace - beta release

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Actual Achievement Date	31/12/2020
Lead Beneficiary/LTP	5. DARIAH ERIC
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Task	All WP7 tasks
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.9

Abstract:

This document reports on the achievement of SSHOC Milestone 43, the beta release of the SSH Open Marketplace. It explains the role of the second release in the development process of the application as well as the community efforts deployed to ensure the uptake of the SSH Open Marketplace by SSH research communities.

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1. Introduction

Three different releases of the SSH Open Marketplace are planned during the SSHOC project. The three corresponding milestones (MS42, 43 and 44) ensure the progress and the coherence of the various tasks contributing to the creation of the SSH Open Marketplace. MS 43 “Marketplace - beta release” is the second one and is described as following in SSHOC Grant Agreement: *“Marketplace implementing core functionality, deployed in an operational environment, populated with an extended set of data, open to the whole community to use and participate”*. This MS report describes the different aspects of SSHOC Work Package 7 activities that contributed to achieve this milestone.

The public instance of the SSH Open Marketplace - accessible at marketplace.sshopencloud.eu - was released at the end of December 2020, and the communication followed mid-January 2021.

2. Description of the Milestone

MS43 was initially described in the SSHOC Grant Agreement as follows: *“Fully functional Marketplace, open to the whole community to use and participate”*. To refine the description and to adapt it to the work performed in WP7 over the course of 2020, a suggestion for changes is included in SSHOC 2nd amendment to the Grant Agreement. The updated means of verification for MS43 is the following: *“Marketplace implementing core functionality, deployed in an operational environment, populated with an extended set of data, open to the whole community to use and participate.”*

2.1. Role of the Milestone

This beta and public release of the SSH Open Marketplace is an important milestone for WP7. Six months after the alpha release (MS42) only available to testers and one year before the final release (MS44), the beta version is a key step in the development schedule for this SSH discovery service. Based on testers' feedback collected between June and December 2020, a new iteration of the SSH Open Marketplace has been developed and released.

2.2. Means of verification

Consultation results and implementation

After the alpha release of the SSH Open Marketplace¹, a series of consultations was held to gather feedback from end-users interested in the development of the portal. Several formats and channels were used - live events, consultation platform, guerrilla interviews - to ensure the quality and diversity of feedback received.

Two **live events** allowed WP7 team to collect feedback from testers and (future) users:

- The “Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: User Workshop”, held the 30th of June 2020 during the ICTeSSH Conference was organised to launch the alpha release. Four testers were selected to present the results of their experience with three dimensions of the alpha version of the Marketplace: UX Design, Navigation and Search experience; Content & curation of content; Curation, trust & governance².
- The “SSH Open Marketplace: Public Consultation for the DARIAH Community”, held the 3d of July 2020 gathered around 25 participants and was a good opportunity for DARIAH community to give feedback, share concerns and make suggestions about the Marketplace³.

In collaboration with WP2, a **consultation platform** was opened for comments from testers for 3 months on the SSHOC website. Three topics were identified to structure the consultation: UX design & Development; Content & Sources; Curation & Governance. 18 answers were collected and used to inform the work of the three related WP7 tasks (T7.2 Development of the Marketplace

¹ See SSHOC website announcement: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/ssh-open-marketplace-alpha-launch> [01.04.2021] and Laure Barbot, Yoann Moranville, Stefan Buddenbohm, Klaus Illmayer, & Matej Ďurčo. (2020). MS42 Marketplace – alpha release (Version v1.0). Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4585699> [01.04.2021]

² See the full report: Laure Barbot, Tracey Biller, Daan Broeder, Ron Dekker, Matej Durco, Irene Vipavc and Marieke Willems, Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: User Workshop, ITM Web Conf., 33 (2020) 04001, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/itmconf/20203304001> [19.04.2021]

³ See notes about the event: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/ssh-open-marketplace-notes-our-public-consultation-dariah> [19.04.2021]

application; T7.3 Marketplace interoperability and T7.4 Governance: population, curation and sustainability).

In parallel, DARIAH/PSNC conducted a series of **guerrilla interviews** with 11 participants, focusing on the design of the portal and aiming at identifying “which functionalities on the website need special attention and care” for the beta version.

This MS report does not aim to present in detail the feedback received, but some important points that have been guiding WP7 work towards the beta version are highlighted in the table below.

	<i>General feedback</i>	<i>Room for improvement</i>
<i>About the design</i>	No major changes are expected by users in terms of design. Beyond the aesthetic preferences that were expressed during the consultations, a very large majority of the testers consulted appreciated the user experience, the clarity of the design and the presentation of the information.	Nevertheless, an effort on the item details view page regarding the item details (i.e., metadata collected for each item) was initiated for the beta release and will be fully implemented for the final release. Based on user feedback, a need for more clarity in the display of metadata has indeed been identified.
<i>About the content</i>	The sources used to populate the beta Marketplace and the ones foreseen for the final release seem to meet testers’ expectations: the four sources highlighted during the consultation - TAPoR, the Standardization Survival Kit, the EOSC catalogue and the CESSDA Training Resources - were already ingested in the beta or in the pipeline for ingestion of the final release.	Datasets population was still very low for the alpha and beta releases, while it is one of the most fundamental items for the social scientists users of the Marketplace. Although the portal does not aim to be exhaustive in terms of datasets, a special effort should be made to better reflect this need.
<i>About the governance and curation</i>	Mechanisms envisioned to support community engagement and data quality of the Marketplace (i.e., major components for its sustainability) have been well received during the consultations. Testers agreed to support a model in which credits and citations should prevail , and the need to build on existing communities was also highlighted.	Although documentation pages of the Marketplace have been updated for the beta version, there are no clear rules of engagement . Furthermore, as the curation work will partly be based on volunteering work, incentives and rewards should be put in place.

All the results of these different consultations - live events, consultation platform and guerilla interviews - were evaluated for their implementation in the beta version of the SSH Open Marketplace. They were then described and grouped in dedicated issues and milestones⁴ in the Gitlab instance used by the development team (T7.2). Four major lines of work guided task 7.2 activities over the last six months of 2020 to prepare the beta release of the Marketplace.

- First, the **implementation of workflows** was improved, and the data model was extended accordingly. As workflows are complex entities in the Marketplace, consisting of a sequence of steps, with optional deeper hierarchy of substeps, the CRUD API was further developed to support this complex data structure, especially supporting specifying related items at the level of the steps. A corresponding dedicated detail view for the workflows has also been developed on the frontend.
- Secondly and as stated above, no major changes in the design were necessary but a few reasonable **layout details were implemented to improve the user experience** for the public release: for example, a new logo for the portal better aligned with the overall SSHOC style guidelines as well as dedicated icons for the five item types were included. Also, a new component on the frontpage was introduced listing a set of recommended items.
- In addition, and to support minimalistic community interaction, the third major line of work was the implementation of a **“report an issue” function**, allowing the users to provide contextualized feedback to any aspect of the Marketplace, be it content or design.
- Finally, the **documentation and static pages** of the SSH Open Marketplace⁵ have also been updated, thanks to the integration of a dedicated Content Management System (CMS)⁶. For this beta release, descriptions of the SSHOC project and its EOSC environment have been prepared. The service, its sources, types of content and main functionalities have been described, and a first definition of the guiding principles and workflows for the curation of the portal have been included. A page dedicated to the implementation of the website covering the more technical aspects has been created and includes minimal information on the API of the Marketplace⁷.

In general, the feedback showed that the technical implementation and the design of the Marketplace is well received. The reviewers were able to navigate the Marketplace as expected. Almost all the issues they reported could be resolved, thus giving proof that the agile development

⁴ See for example the collection of feedback related to the design: <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/groups/sshoc/-/milestones/>; and the milestone dedicated to the beta release: <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/groups/sshoc/-/milestones/5> [23.04.2021]

⁵ SSH Open Marketplace About pages: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/about> [01.04.2021]

⁶ See Gitlab issue frontend #28: <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/sshoc/sshoc-marketplace-frontend/-/issues/28> [01.04.2021]

⁷ See “About the technical aspects” page of the SSH Open Marketplace: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/about/implementation> [01.04.2021]

workflow is able to cover further implementation challenges. The established technical infrastructure allows sustainable adaptations of the data model and the integration of new features. At the same time, the work distribution between the partners proves to be efficient.

Extended set of data

Data ingestion

The beta version of the Marketplace contains **4 763 individual items**:

- 1 606 Tools & Services
- 140 Training Materials
- 2 986 Publications
- 2 Datasets
- 29 Workflows

Search results (4763)

Refine your search [Clear filters](#) Sort by last modification ◄ Previous 1 of 239 Next ►

CATEGORIES

<input type="checkbox"/> Tools & Services	1606
<input type="checkbox"/> Training Materials	140
<input type="checkbox"/> Publications	2986
<input type="checkbox"/> Datasets	2
<input type="checkbox"/> Workflows	29

ACTIVITIES

<input type="checkbox"/> Analyzing	576
<input type="checkbox"/> Visual Analysis	303
<input type="checkbox"/> Content Analysis	226
<input type="checkbox"/> Discovering	171
<input type="checkbox"/> Capturing	150
<input type="checkbox"/> Enriching	122
<input type="checkbox"/> Gathering	116
<input type="checkbox"/> Annotating	112
<input type="checkbox"/> Disseminating	112
<input type="checkbox"/> Collaborating	87

[More...](#)

Data Dictionary Generator (DDG)
 Activities: Collaborating, Writing, Content Analysis
 Aimed at the TEI editing community and intended to be run inside oXygen, the Data Dictionary Generator (DDG) generates profiles of every element and attribute appearing in a TEI file. Each entry includes a definition from the TEI Guidelines, a local, project-specific definition...
[Read more](#)

eLexicon. Dictionary of Polish Medieval Latin - from TEI encoding to an eXist-db application
 No description provided.
[Read more](#)

Create a dictionary in TEI
 Activities: Encoding
 Keywords: TEI, recommended
 This scenario sets out the best practices for creating a born-digital dictionary, especially with the TEI (Text Encoding Initiative). However, building a standardized lexicographical dataset is not only a data format problem, it is also an intellectual and technical process...
[Read more](#)

Fig. 1 - Screenshot of the research results section on the SSH Open Marketplace

This data population is the result of a layered process where first an extensive list of possible sources for the Marketplace was compiled. Then this list was ordered by priorities, ensuring that already in the first couple of sources there was a mix between different types of items (tools, publications, and workflows). In the first phase of ingestion until the beta release of the Marketplace the **ingestion of six major sources** was achieved: TAPoR⁸, the Programming

⁸ TAPoR website: <http://tapor.ca/home> [22.01.2021]

Historian⁹, the EOSC Portal¹⁰, SSK Workflows¹¹ and Resources¹², the Language Resource Switchboard¹³ and publications from DH Conferences¹⁴ and journals¹⁵ retrieved from DBLP - and a few manual additions. As the ingestion pipeline provided by Semantic Web Company (SWC) was already functional and tested with the alpha release¹⁶, the mapping of the various metadata categories from the sources to the SSH Marketplace data model and subsequent ingestion was executed in this way. In the coming phases alternative ways of ingestion will be investigated as well.

Data quality

Furthermore, to ensure minimal data quality for the beta release, a few curation tasks were conducted. First, because a new version of the **vocabulary used for the 'activity' property**, TaDiRAH, was released in 2020¹⁷, and because the majority of the concepts used for this property in the alpha version of the Marketplace - coming from TAPoR - were using the previous version of TaDiRAH, a mapping exercise between both versions and a cleaning exercise of the concepts used in the Marketplace have been conducted in the SWC PoolParty Vocabulary Manager. Then, thanks to the review of the TAPoR source ingestion conducted via a Python notebook developed by CNR¹⁸, T7.3 and T7.4 teams were able to identify 132 **broken links** among the TAPoR ingested items. These links were classified based on the errors' type they were pointing to, manually curated and the result of this manual curation was then re-ingested in the Marketplace. Finally, to present a complete homepage to the end-user for the public release, a set of 10 items - 2 per item type - was chosen, manually enriched, and ingested as **recommended items** for the home page.

⁹ The Programming Historian website: <https://programminghistorian.org/> [22.01.2021]

¹⁰ EOSC catalogue and marketplace: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/> [22.01.2021]

¹¹ Standardization Survival Kit: <http://ssk.huma-num.fr/#/> [22.01.2021]

¹² Standardization Survival Kit Zotero library: <https://www.zotero.org/groups/427927/ssk-parthenos/collections/ZIVPVK66> [22.01.2021]

¹³ CLARIN Switchboard: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools> [22.01.2021]

¹⁴ Digital Humanities Conference proceedings on DBLP: <https://dblp.org/db/conf/dihu/index.html> [22.01.2021]

¹⁵ Digital Scholarship in the Humanities journal on DBLP: <https://dblp.org/db/journals/lalc/index.html> [22.01.2021]

¹⁶ See MS42 - alpha release report: Laure Barbot, Yoann Moranville, Stefan Buddenbohm, Klaus Illmayer, & Matej Ďurčo. (2020). MS42 Marketplace - alpha release (Version v1.0). Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4585699> [01.04.2021]

¹⁷ Borek, L., Hastik, C., Khramova, V., Geiger, J. (Eds.), 2020, 28. September, TaDiRAH: Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities. Version 2.0.0, <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/> (CC 0). See also OpenMethods Spotlights #2 : Interview with Luise Borek and Canan Hastik about TaDiRAH, <https://openmethods.dariah.eu/2021/02/10/openmethods-spotlights-2-interview-with-luise-borek-and-canan-hastik-about-tadirah/> [23.04.2021]

¹⁸ See Review of data ingested from TAPoR (draft) notebook: <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/sshoc/data-ingestion/-/blob/master/repositories/tapor/tools/TAPoRCheck.ipynb> [23.04.2021]

Recommended

Tools & Services [See all](#)

 Gephi

Activities: Analyzing, Network Analysis, Relational Analysis, Visual Analysis, Modeling, Capturing, Spatial Analysis, Discovering, Content Analysis
 Keywords: recommended

Gephi is the leading visualization and exploration software for all kinds of graphs and networks. Gephi is open-source and free. Runs on Windows, Mac OS X and Linux.

[Read more](#)

 AntConc

Activities: Discovering, Analyzing, Structural Analysis, Concordance
 Keywords: recommended

AntConc is free concordance software. It is multi-platform and easy to deploy and use. AntConc is part of a suite of related tools for text processing and analysis, including applications for parallel corpus analysis, word profiling, PDF to text conversion, text structure...

[Read more](#)

Training Materials [See all](#)

 Corpus Analysis with AntconC

Activities: Analyzing, Content Analysis, Interpreting, Contextualizing
 Keywords: distant-reading, recommended

This lesson introduces how to use AntconC software to conduct corpus analysis with the AntconC software. Corpus analysis is a form of text analysis which allows you to make comparisons between textual objects at a large scale (so-called 'distant reading'). You will learn to do...

[Read more](#)

 Exploring and Analyzing Network Data with Python

Activities: Network Analysis
 Keywords: recommended

This lesson introduces network metrics and how to draw conclusions from them when working with humanities data. You will learn how to use the NetworkX Python package to produce and work with these network statistics.

[Read more](#)

Fig. 2 - Screenshot of the recommended items section on the SSH Open Marketplace homepage

These curation activities and the work conducted in other SSHOC WPs - especially WP3 “Lifting Technologies and Services into the SSH Cloud”, have contributed to enhance the quality of items, but also as a side effect have led to some modifications and clarifications of the data model. For example, based on the work conducted within T3.6 “Making Data Re-usable and Actionable” a series of collaborative use cases between the SSH Open Marketplace and the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry have been designed¹⁹ allowing among other things to highlight the importance of the MIME type for datasets in the Marketplace in order to invoke the Switchboard directly from the Marketplace. These considerations, even if they are not “visible” in the beta version of the Marketplace, are crucial to ensure that next steps in Marketplace development will be taken based on the expertise and recommendations provided by other SSHOC WPs. Another output of the curation work undertaken for the beta release was a first draft of the curation workflow with a definition of roles and activities (e.g., for moderators and

¹⁹ Buddenbohm, Stefan, Broeder, Daan, Eisner, Marthe Irene, Illmayer, Klaus, & Durco, Matej. (2020, November 5). Collaborative Use Cases between SSH Open Marketplace and the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312708> [23.04.2021]

contributors) associated with an initial version of editorial guidelines that will be finalised for the next release of the portal.

3. Conclusions and next steps

The beta release of the SSH Open Marketplace at the end of December 2020 was an important synchronisation point between the different tasks working to create the portal. This first public version with which users can interact - even if only via a “report an issue” function - was a new step in the iterative process of development. It now gives one year to the SSHOC WP7 team to prepare the final release (planned for December 2021), and the challenges to overcome during this period have already been identified. The final release of the Marketplace will be supported by a stable and sustainable ingestion pipeline and several solutions will be tested in parallel over the course of 2021. A set of new data sources to ingest will be prioritised, SSHOC outputs (services and training) being one of the first sources on the list. The curation components will be developed and implemented allowing users to fully interact with the Marketplace, thus increasing data quality and relevance for SSH researchers, which is one of the guarantees for a successful and sustainable portal in the long run.